

Pharmacological studies on the QURANI plants' mixture (a new pharmaceutical product)

Eman A. Alam

Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

ABSTRACT

QURANI plants' mixture is a new pharmaceutical product composed of some edible and medicinal plants (15 plants) mentioned in the Holy QURAN (in a certain percentage, according to that is mentioned in Patent no.1429/2013, presented to the Academy of Scientific Research and Technology, Egypt). The main aim of this work is to study hepatocurative, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, diuretic and antipyretic effects of this new pharmaceutical product, in addition to toxicological studies on this product and its side effects on many important organs of the body of all investigated rats. *In vitro* studies were carried out to check anticancer (prostate and colon cancer) effects of the product, in addition to *in vivo* studies by feeding adult female albino rats under investigation with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of the product were carried out also to check hepatocurative, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, diuretic and antipyretic activities of this product and finally toxicological studies and investigation of histological structures of some important organs (Heart, Brain, Kidney, Intestine, Lung, Spleen, Stomach and Colon) of investigated rats were done also in order to check any bad side effects of this new pharmaceutical product. Results of both *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies showed that, all investigated doses have hepatocurative, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, diuretic and antipyretic effects, these effects have dose dependent manner. Toxicological studies and examination of all important organs of all investigated rats revealed that, this product is too safe at all the studied doses. Preliminary phytochemical screening of the crude extract of this pharmaceutical product revealed its richness of many valuable secondary metabolites such as: flavonoids, anthraquinones, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, cardiac glycosides etc., These Results will lead us to more biological and chemical investigations of this new, cheap and safe pharmaceutical natural product.

Citation: Alam EA (2017). Pharmacological studies on the QURANI plants' mixture (a new pharmaceutical product). *World Journal of Biomedicine and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2: 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.837354>

Received May 7, 2017; **Accepted** July 2, 2017; **Published** August 1, 2017.

Copyright: © 2017 Alam EA. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. WJBPS is a journal publication of BRSF.

Competing Interests: The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

* **E-mail:** aalam.eman@gmail.com

This research work was presented at the Biosciences Research Support Foundation (BRSF)'s 2nd International Conference on Biosciences Research (ICBR), Owerri, Nigeria, 24-27 November 2016.

Keywords: pharmacological studies; edible and medicinal plants; QURANI plants' mixture; histological studies; toxicological studies; secondary metabolites

1. INTRODUCTION

QURANI plants' mixture is a new pharmaceutical product composed of some edible and medicinal plants (15 plants) mentioned in the Holy QURAN (in a certain percentage, according to that is implemented in Patent no. 1429/2013, presented to the Academy of Scientific Research and Technology, Egypt).

These fifteen edible plants, used to prepare this new mixture were cited in the holy QURAN as follows: Sûrat Al-Baqarah (The Cow): (61, 266);

Sûrat Al-An'âm (The Cattle): (99, 141); Sûrat Ar-Ra'd (The Thunder): (4); Sûrat An-Nahl: (11); Sûrat Al-Kahf (The Cave): (32); Sûrat Maryam (Mary): (23-26); Sûrat Al-Anbiyâ (The Prophets): (47); Sûrat Al-Mu'minûn (The Believers): (18-20); Sûrat An-Nûr (The Light): (35); Sûrat Ash-Shu'arâ (The Poets): (146-148); Sûrat uqmân: (16); Sûrat Saba' (Sheba): (16); Sûrat Yâ-Sîn: (33-35, 57); Sûrat As-Sâffât (Those Ranged in Ranks): (146); Sûrat Sâd: (51); Sûrat Az-Zukhruf (The Gold Adornments): (73); Sûrat Qâf: (10); Sûrat At-Tûr (The Mount): (22); Sûrat Ar-Rahmân (The Most Gracious): (10-13, 37, 52, 68); Sûrat Al-Wâqî'ah (The Event): (20, 28-

29, 32, 89); Sûrat Al-Insân or Ad-Dhr (Man or Time): (17); Sûrat Al-Mursalât (Those Sent Forth): (42); Sûrat An-Naba' (The Great News): (32); Sûrat 'Abasa (He Frowned): (27-31); Sûrat At-Tîn (The Fig):(1).

The presented review aimed at reviewing some results of biological studies on the Holy QURANI plants' mixture (a new pharmaceutical product) including toxicological studies and evaluation of hepatocurative, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, diuretic and antipyretic activities of this new pharmaceutical product, in addition to phytochemical screening of its crude extract [1-8].

This review is the first part of upcoming series of reviews, trying to match between the Holy QURAN verses and modern sciences regarding plants. These reviews are dealing with the Holy QURAN not merely as a religious book only, but also as a scientific book. By examining all plants mentioned in the Holy QURAN, you will know how the Holy QURAN is great and introduced many useful medicinal and healthy edible plants; all verses of the Holy QURAN did not include toxic or harmful plants at all. Finally at the end of this review, please say SubhanAllah.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Sugar, kidney and liver functions and lipid profile of long period of feeding rats with high doses of the QURANI plants' mixture (1, 2, 3 = groups of rats feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture during 45 days, 4= control, n= 6 rats).

N	Sugar	Kidney function		Liver function		Lipid profile			
	Glu.	Urea	Creat.	ALT	AST	Choles.	Trigly.	HDL	LDL
1	20	23.4	0.65	49.6	41	126.2	105.2	37.8	67.4
	±0.12	±0.43	±0.01	±1.40	±2.20	±3.20	±2.25	±0.65	±0.89
2	23.4	28.6	0.59	47.8	46.4	124.6	126.6	32.8	51
	±0.13	±0.50	±0.02	±1.53	±2.15	±2.90	±3.12	±0.87	±0.63
3	30.6	32.6	0.56	51	46	115.2	91.2	35.8	61
	±0.12	±0.52	±0.01	±1.36	±1.95	±3.15	±2.71	±0.69	±0.58
4	28.4	34	0.53	47	44	129.4	157.8	32.6	65.2
	±0.20	±0.56	±0.02	±1.28	±2.30	±4.25	±3.35	±0.78	±0.71
L.S.D	0.73	1.02	0.63	3.02	4.33	4.53	3.99	1.99	2.03
-0.05									
L.S.D	1.13	1.65	1.15	4.23	5.23	5.61	4.98	4	3.1
-0.01									

The following are results of biological studies on the QURANI plants' mixture including toxicological studies and evaluation of hepatocurative, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, diuretic and antipyretic activities of this new pharmaceutical product.

2.1 Toxicological studies on the QURANI plants' mixture [7]

2.1.1 Hematological studies

Hematological analyses showed that, feeding rats with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture during 45 days has normal effects on liver and kidney functions and CBCs profile; this mixture has good effects on glucose ratios, platelets and lipid profile of the blood of all examined rats (Tables 1-2).

2.1.2 Urine analyses profile of long period of feeding rats with high doses of the QURANI plants' mixture

Studies of urine analyses revealed that, feeding rats with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture during 45 days has normal effects on chemical and physical characters of urine of all examined rats (Table.3).

Table 2. Blood CBCs profile of long period of feeding rats with high doses of the QURANI plants' mixture (1, 2, 3 = groups of rats feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture during 45 days, 4= control, n= 6 rats).

N	Blood CBCs							
	Hb.	RBCs.	Ht (PCV)	MCV	MCH	MCHc	WBCs.	Platelets
1	14.06	4.24	38.6	90.8	32.6	36	3,620	167,40
	±0.35	±0.13	±0.21	±1.23	±1.52	±1.63	±5.60	±10.73
2	14.36	4.34	38.4	90.4	33	36.6	4,722	172,20
	±0.42	±0.20	±0.18	±1.29	±1.25	±1.75	±6.23	±9.63
3	13.22	4	36.4	89.6	32.2	35.8	4,454	157.6
	±0.50	±0.15	±0.19	±1.16	±1.21	±1.83	±7.51	±6.28
4	14.24	4.15	37.6	90	34	37.4	3,500	129.4
	±0.74	±0.16	±0.24	±1.09	±1.63	±1.98	±8.54	±10.24
L.S.D.								
-0.05	0.83	0.3	0.32	1.96	2.33	2.95	8.9	9.21
L.S.D.								
-0.01	1.73	0.65	0.54	3.01	3.12	3.43	9.83	9.95

Table 3. Urine Analyses profile of long period of feeding rats with high doses of the QURANI plants' mixture (1= control, 2, 3 and 4 = groups of rats feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture during 45 days, n= 6 rats).

N	Color	SP. GR.	pH	Sugar	Acetone	Albumin	Bile Pig.	Blood	Pus	Crystals
1	Yellow	1005	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	Yellow	1005	9	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	Yellow	1000	9	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
4	Yellow	1000	9	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

2.1.3 Weights of some important organs

Based on organs weights' estimation (in grams), it was found that, all investigated doses (2, 4 and 8 g/kg) of the QURANI plants' mixture have not any bad side effects on many important organs (Heart, Brain, Kidney, Liver, Lung, Spleen, Stomach and Colon) of all examined rats (Table 4).

2.1.4 Histological studies

Based on histological examination, it was found that, all investigated doses (2, 4 and 8 g/kg) of the QURANI plants' mixture have not any bad side effects on many important organs (Brain, Liver, Stomach, Colon, Lung, Heart, Kidney, Spleen and Intestine) of all examined rats (Figures 1-9).

Table 4. Weights (in grams) of some important organs (Brain, Heart and Lung, Liver, Kidney, Spleen and Stomach) of investigated rats (1= Control, 2, 3, 4 = groups of rats feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg/day, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture during 45 days, n= 6 rats).

Organs	Groups			
	1	2	3	4
Brain	0.91 ±0.120	0.946 ±0.110	1.404 ±0.112	1.04 ±0.133
Heart+	1.198	1.99	2	1.64
Lung	±0.100	±0.131	±0.146	±0.120
Liver	5.494 ±0.210	3.584 ±0.210	5.104 ±0.224	5.98 ±0.236
Kidney	0.409 ±0.070	0.447 ±0.054	0.482 ±0.060	0.427 ±0.051
Spleen	0.412 ±0.060	0.507 ±0.042	0.584 ±0.041	0.45 ±0.042
Stomach	1.145 ±0.120	1.218 ±0.163	1.966 ±0.134	0.876 ±0.113
L.S.D	0.25	0.11	0.22	0.14
-0.05				
L.S.D.	0.32	0.22	0.31	0.19
-0.01				

Figure 1. A photomicrograph of a section in a brain of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x= 200).

Figure 2. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x= 200).

Figure 3. A photomicrograph of a section in a stomach of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x=200).

Figure 4. A photomicrograph of a section in a colon of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 5. A photomicrograph of a section in a lung of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 6. A photomicrograph of a section in a heart of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x=100).

Figure 7. A photomicrograph of a section in a kidney of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x=100).

Figure 8. A photomicrograph of a section in a spleen of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 9. A photomicrograph of a section in an Intestine of rat feeding with 8 g/kg of the QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histological structures (Haematoxylin& Eosin stain, x=100).

2.2 Hepatoprotective and hepatocurative effects of the QURANI plants' mixture [6]

2.2.1 Hematological studies

Hematological analyses showed that, feeding rats with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture has good effects on liver functions of all examined rats (Tables 5-6).

Table 5 (A, B). Studies of the hepatoprotective effect of the QURANI plants' mixture by estimation of liver functions of investigated rats (n= 6 rats).**A-** Determination of liver functions of investigated rats at the beginning of the experiment (before any treatment):

Liver functions				
N	ALT	AST	Alkaline phosphatase	Albumin
A	4.35±	5.85±	44.00±	2.65±
	0.11	0.13	1.02	0.1
B	6.50±	9.80±	55.50±	2.54±
	0.15	0.19	1.33	0.09
C	15.00±	13.50±	77.90±	2.80±
	0.23	0.22	2.33	0.11
D	6.35±	9.40±	55.00±	3.00±
	0.19	0.21	1.4	0.13
E	25.30±	23.00±	101.00±	3.15±
	0.5	0.48	3	0.14
F	10.00±	12.00±	57.60±	3.20±
	0.3	0.36	2.1	0.14
L.S.D. (0.05)	0.51	0.57	3.36	0.21
L.S.D. (0.01)	0.72	0.8	5.57	0.34

B- Determination of liver functions of investigated rats after 4 weeks of feeding rats with the QURANI plants' mixture along with injecting them with CCL₄ (in order to induce fibrosis): (A) = groups of rats treated with Silymarin, (B, C, D) = groups of rats feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture, (E) = groups of rats injected with CCL₄ without any treatment, F= Control group.

Liver functions				
N	ALT	AST	Alkaline phosphatase	Albumin
A	41.75±	49.75±	107.75±	3.04±
	1.33	1.25	0.19	0.08
B	41.75±	41.25±	101.60±	3.38±
	1.41	1.39	3.57	0.08
C	38.66±	39.00±	95.20±	3.47±
	1.26	1.3	3.47	0.09
D	34.00±	41.00±	92.20±	3.47±
	1.41	1.39	2	0.19
E	51.33±	49.33±	91.67±	2.93±
	1.73	2	2.14	0.2
F	38.67±	37.00±	89.20±	3.34±
	1.5	1.42	2.36	0.22
L.S.D (0.05)	2.4	3.14	3.23	0.31
L.S.D. (0.01)	3.4	4.57	4.98	0.41

Table 6 (A, B,C). Studies of the hepatocurative effect of the QURANI plants' mixture by estimating liver functions of investigated rats (n= 6 rats).**A-** Determination of liver functions of investigated rats at the beginning of the experiment (before any treatment):

Liver functions				
N	ALT	AST	Alkaline phosphatase	Albumin
A	3.500±	6.00±	45.80±	2.78±
	1.02	1.1	3.33	0.09
B	6.25±	10.00±	55.00±	2.64±
	1.8	2	3.52	0.08
C	14.40±	13.33±	79.20±	2.9
	2	2.01	3.75	±0.07
D	6.00±	9.25±	53.60±	3.10±
	1.93	1.99	3.24	0.09
E	24.67	22.80±	100.33±	3.20±
	3.04	3.2	3.99	1.01
F	9.75±	11.67±	57.00±	3.26±
	1.94	2.59	3.07	1.11
L.S.D. (0.05)	2.55	2.7	3.94	1.33
L.S.D. (0.01)	4.1	3.99	5	2

B- Determination of liver functions of investigated rats after 4 weeks of injection of all groups of rats with CCL₄ , to induce fibrosis in rats under investigation (A-E), except the control group (F).

Liver functions				
N	ALT	AST	Alkaline phosphatase	Albumin
A	24.25±	27.67	56.67±	3.20±
	3.31	±3.00	3.47	0.1
B	28.80±	33.67±	87.67	3.02±
	3.01	3.12	3.92	0.14
C	30.25±	31.67±	89.20±	3.03±
	3.45	3.37	3.89	0.13
D	27.33±	28.33±	95.40±	3.17±
	3.26	2.99	3.96	0.12
E	27.40±	30.25±	98.60±	3.00±
	3.3	3.06	3.87	0.1
F	26.80±	27.40±	88.00±	3.125±
	3.23	2.97	3.79	0.11
L.S.D. (0.05)	4.04	3.5	4.25	0.2
L.S.D. (0.01)	5.78	5.5	6	0.32

C- Determination of liver functions of investigated rats after 4 weeks of feeding rats with the QURANI plants' mixture (following the induction of fibrosis in rats by injecting them with CCL₄ during 4 weeks). (A) = groups of rats treated with Silymarin, (B, C, D) = groups of rats feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg, respectively of the QURANI plants' mixture, (E) = groups of rats injected with CCL₄ only, F= Control group.

Liver functions				
N	ALT	AST	Alkaline phosphatase	Albumin
A	66.50± 3.07	65.25± 3.14	138.67± 4.33	2.81± 0.17
B	61.33± 3.1	63.00± 3.23	132.00± 4.56	3.34± 0.18
C	60.50± 3.2	59.00± 3.36	128.50± 4.27	3.27± 0.17
D	64.50± 2.99	63.50± 3.46	135.00± 4.37	3.34± 0.19
E	64.67± 3.05	64.33± 3.75	132.00± 4.28	3.33± 0.2
F	50.60± 2.78	47.60± 2.97	111.60± 3.97	3.36± 0.21
L.S.D. (0.05)	3.75	4	4.53	0.25
L.S.D. (0.01)	5.51	5.9	6.01	0.39

2.3 Histological studies

2.3.1 Histological studies on liver of rats under investigation

2.3.1.1 Hepatoprotective effects of the QURANI plants' mixture

Based on histological examination, it was found that, all investigated doses (2, 4 and 8 g/kg) of the QURANI plants' mixture have hepatoprotective effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄, this effect is a dose dependent effect (Figures 10-13).

Figure 10. A Photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat showing moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x = 100).

Figure 11. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 2g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing hepatoprotective effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x = 100).

Figure 12. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 4g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing hepatoprotective effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x= 100).

Figure 13. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing hepatoprotective effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x= 100).

2.3.1.2 Hepatocurative effects of the QURANI plants' mixture

Based on histological examination, it was found that, all investigated doses (2, 4 and 8 g/kg) of

the QURANI plants' mixture have hepatocurative effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄, this effect is a dose dependent effect (Figures 14-17).

Figure 14. A Photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat showing moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x= 100).

Figure 15. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 2g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing hepatocurative effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x= 100).

Figure 16. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 4g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing hepatocurative effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x= 100).

Figure17. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing hepatocurative effects against moderate liver fibrosis induced by the injection with CCl₄ (Mason stain, x= 100).

2.3.1.3 Histological studies on many other important organs of rats under investigation

Based on histological examination, it was found that, feeding rats with all investigated doses (2, 4 and 8 g/kg) of the QURANI plants' mixture along with or after injecting them with CCl₄ have not any bad side effects on many other important organs (Heart, Brain, Kidney, Intestine, Lung, Spleen, Stomach and Colon) of all examined rats. In addition to the induction of moderate liver fibrosis in this study, CCl₄

induced many side effects such as: inflammation in colon and lung tissues, few scattered lymphocytes were also observed in brain tissues, follicular hyperplasia was occurred in spleen tissues and mild focal degeneration of heart muscles was observed also. These side effects are well treated by feeding these rats with all investigated doses (2, 4 and 8 g/kg) of the QURANI plants' mixture along with or after injecting them with CCl₄, this effect has a dose dependent manner (Figures 18-31).

These results are agreed with other previous results of studies on anti-inflammatory effects of this new pharmaceutical product, previous results revealed that, this product can be considered as a new good anti-inflammatory

agent which has not any bad side effects on histological structures of all examined important organs of rats under investigation (Liver, Heart, Brain, Kidney, Lung, Spleen, Stomach and Colon) [4].

Figure 18. A photomicrograph of a section in a colon of rat showing an inflammation resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl₄ (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 19. A photomicrograph of a section in a colon of rat showing the anti-inflammatory effect of feeding rat with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture against an inflammation resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl₄ (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 20. A photomicrograph of a section in a lung of rat showing an inflammation resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl₄ (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 21. A photomicrograph of a section in a lung of rat showing the anti-inflammatory effect of feeding rat with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture against an inflammation resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times= 100$).

Figure 22. A photomicrograph of a section in a brain of rat showing few scattered lymphocytes in brain tissues resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times= 100$).

Figure 23. A photomicrograph of a section in a brain of rat showing few scattered lymphocytes in brain tissues resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times= 400$).

Figure 24. A photomicrograph of a section in a brain of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing that, scattered lymphocytes resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 were totally disappeared (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times= 100$).

Figure 25. A photomicrograph of a section in a spleen of rat showing moderate follicular hyperplasia in spleen tissues resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times=100$).

Figure 26. A photomicrograph of a section in a spleen of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing that, follicular hyperplasia in spleen tissues resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 were totally treated (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times=100$).

Figure 27. A photomicrograph of a section in a heart of rat showing mild focal degeneration of heart muscle fibers resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times=400$).

Figure 28. A photomicrograph of a section in a heart of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing that, mild focal degeneration of heart muscle fibers resulted as a side effect of the injection with CCl_4 was treated (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, $\times=100$).

Figure 29. A photomicrograph of a section in a stomach of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 30. A photomicrograph of a section in a kidney of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 31. A photomicrograph of a section in an intestine of rat feeding with 8g/kg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

2.4 Anti-inflammatory effects of QURANI plants' mixture [4]

2.4.1 Anti-inflammatory effects of QURANI plants' mixture

In vivo studies of the anti-inflammatory effects of feeding adult female albino rats under investigation with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI

plants' mixture showed that, both edema sizes and weights are decreased in case of feeding these rats with all investigated doses of QURANI plants' mixture. The highest anti-inflammatory effect was obtained by feeding with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture based on the estimation edema weight and 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture based on the estimation edema size (Table 7).

Table 7. Anti-inflammatory effects of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of induction of inflammation {1= Control, 2= Injected group of rats with carragenan, 3, 4, 5 = Groups of rats those feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture, respectively and 6 = Positive control group of rats (administered Ibuprofen, 100 mg/kg)}, (n= 6 rats).

Estimation of Inflammation	Groups					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Weight of paw (gm)	-	0.703±0.090	0.353±0.070	0.393±0.050	0.256±0.020	0.554±0.060
% of change of weight of paw	-	0.000±0.000	49.787±0.453	44.097±0.513	63.585±0.759	21.195±0.202
Volume of paw (Cm ³)	-	0.500±0.004	0.180±0.003	0.220±0.001	0.220±0.002	0.380±0.006
% of change of volume of paw	-	0.000±0.000	64.000±0.309	56.000±0.409	56.000±0.567	24.000±0.203
L.S.D. (0.05)		0.323	1.34	2	2.311	0.722
L.S.D. (0.01)		0.538	1.96	3.032	3.501	1.115

2.4.2 Weights of some important organs of the body of investigated rats

Data in Table 8 shows that, there is not any bad side effects on weights of all examined

important organs (Brain, Heart and Lung, Liver, Kidney, Spleen and Stomach) of the body of all rats under investigation by feeding them with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture.

Table 8. Weights (gm) of some important organs (brain, heart and lung, liver, kidney, spleen and stomach) of investigated rats after 24 hours of induction of inflammation {1= Control, 2= Injected group of rats with carragenan, 3, 4, 5 = groups of rats those feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture, respectively and 6 = positive control group of rats (administered Ibuprofen, 100 mg/kg)}, (n= 6 rats).

Organs	Groups						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
Brain	0.910±0.120	1.682±0.120	1.292±0.110	1.440±0.130	1.432±0.109	1.090±0.107	
Heart+Lung	1.198±0.100	0.868±0.133	1.365±0.145	1.390±0.122	0.135±1.359	1.070±0.129	
Liver	5.494±0.210	5.386±0.220	6.077±0.225	5.780±0.235	5.303±0.225	4.374±0.237	
Kidney	0.409±0.070	0.494±0.050	0.325±0.062	0.363±0.050	0.395±0.040	0.582±0.056	
Spleen	0.412±0.060	0.556±0.040	0.437±0.040	0.416±0.040	0.336±0.060	0.370±0.060	
Stomach	1.145±0.120	1.308±0.160	1.508±0.135	1.400±0.115	1.606±0.123	1.425±0.148	
L.S.D.(0.05)		1	0.722	0.933	1.051	0.971	1.13
L.S.D. (0.01)		1.531	1.22	1.315	1.602	1.401	1.651

2.4.3 Histological studies on some important organs of the body of investigated rats

Results of histological studies on important organs of all investigated rats revealed that, inducing inflammation by injecting rats with carragenan, followed by feeding these rats with 2, 4 or 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture have not any bad side effect on the histological structures of these organs (Heart, Brain, Kidney, Liver, Spleen, Stomach, Colon and Lung).

Figures 32-40 show the normal histological structures of heart, brain, kidney, liver, spleen, stomach, colon and lung of inflamed rats

(inflammation was induced by injecting these rats with carragenan) after feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture as a good anti-inflammatory agent.

It is well observed from histological studies included in this work that, pneumonia was occurred as a side effect of inducing inflammation (inflammation was induced by injecting rats with carragenan into the sub-planter surface of the right hind paw), this side effect was treated by all investigated doses of QURANI plants' mixture. 4 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture was found to be the best dose in this regard (Figures 39-40).

Figure 32. A photomicrograph of a section in a brain of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=200).

Figure 33. A photomicrograph of a section in a heart of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=100).

Figure 34. A photomicrograph of a section in a kidney of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=100).

Figure 35. A photomicrograph of a section in a liver of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=400).

Figure 36. A photomicrograph of a section in a spleen of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=100).

Figure 37. A photomicrograph of a section in a stomach of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=200).

Figure 38. A photomicrograph of a section in a colon of rat feeding with 2 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing normal histological structure (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x= 100).

Figure 39. A photomicrograph of a section in a lung of an inflamed non treated rats after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing pneumonia as a side effect (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=100).

Figure 40. A photomicrograph of a section in a lung of rat feeding with 4 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture after 24 hours of the induction of an inflammation showing that, good effect on treating pneumonia was obtained using this dose (Haematoxylin & Eosin stain, x=100).

2.5 Cytotoxic effect of ethanolic extract of QURANI plants' mixture against PC3 and HCT116 cell lines [3]

In vitro studies of ethanolic extract of QURANI plants' mixture revealed the cytotoxic effect of this extract against both human prostate (PC3) and colon (HCT116) cancer cell lines. Inhibition caused by using 100 $\mu\text{l/ml}$ (this volume is related to 25 μg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture)

of this extract reached to 36.300 ± 0.085 and 76.300 ± 0.045 against HCT116 and PC3 cell lines, respectively. IC_{50} of this extract against PC3 cell line equals 44.60 $\mu\text{l/ml}$ (this volume is related to 11.15 μg d.w. of QURANI plants' mixture), but it cannot be detected in case of HCT116 cell line using these investigated concentrations of this extract (Table 9 and Figures 41-42).

Table 9. Cytotoxicity of ethanolic extract of QURANI plants' mixture against PC3 and HCT116 cell lines (n=6).

Concentrations $\mu\text{L/ml}$	Surviving rate (Mean \pm SD)		% of inhibition (Mean \pm SD)	
	PC3	HCT116	PC3	HCT116
0.000	1.000 \pm 0.043	1.000 \pm 0.072	0.000 \pm 0.043	0.000 \pm 0.072
12.500	0.919 \pm 0.078	0.974 \pm 0.079	8.100 \pm 0.078	3.000 \pm 0.079
25.000	0.711 \pm 0.069	0.877 \pm 0.036	28.900 \pm 0.069	12.300 \pm 0.036
50.000	0.443 \pm 0.065	0.834 \pm 0.091	55.700 \pm 0.065	16.600 \pm 0.091
100.000	0.237 \pm 0.045	0.637 \pm 0.085	76.300 \pm 0.045	36.300 \pm 0.085

Figure 41. IC₅₀ of PC₃ by ethanolic extract of QURANI plants' mixture.

Figure 42: IC₅₀ of HCT116 by ethanolic extract of QURANI plants' mixture.

2.5.1 Diuretic effect of QURANI plants' mixture [3]

In vivo studies of the diuretic effect of daily feeding rats with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showed that, the amount of urine increased by increasing the amount of this mixture when compared to the control group. It was observed that, the average daily increase in the volume of urine of the rat (compared to the control group) reached to 1.85 ml/day after feeding with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture.

Results of kidney functions and urine analyses revealed that, this mixture has not any bad side effects in this regard, moreover rats feeding with QURANI plants' mixture have better kidney functions (urea and creatinine are lower in case of rats those daily feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture than those of control group). Rats fed with this mixture are also having normal urine physical and chemical characters compared to the control group (Tables 10-12).

Table10. Amount of urine during 4 days (1, 2, 3 = 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture, respectively, 4= Control and 5 = Positive control (Lafurex: Furoseme Ampules, 40 mg/kg/day), n= 6 rats.

Treatments	Days				Average volume/day	Average daily volume/rat
	1	2	3	4		
1	7.50	70.00	20.0	25.00	30.63	6.13
2	35.00	45.00	70.00	45.00	49.00	9.80
3	60.00	70.00	57.00	40.00	56.75	11.35
4	35.00	45.00	50.00	60.00	47.50	9.500
5	10.00	17.00	15.00	25.00	16.75	3.35

Table 11 (a, b, c and d). Urine analyses during 4 days (1, 2, 3 = 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture, respectively, 4= Control and 5 = Positive control (Lafurex: Furosemide Ampules, 40 mg/kg/day), n= 6 rats.

a- The 1st day										
N	Color	SP. GR.	pH	Sugar	Acetone	Albumin	Bile Pig.	Blood	Pus	Crystals
1	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	Yellow	1025	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
4	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
5	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
b- The 2nd day:										
N	Color	SP. GR.	pH	Sugar	Acetone	Albumin	Bile Pig.	Blood	Pus	Crystals
1	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	Yellow	1025	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
4	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
5	Yellow	1000	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
c- The 3rd day:										
N	Color	SP. GR.	pH	Sugar	Acetone	Albumin	Bile Pig.	Blood	Pus	Crystals
1	Yellow	1005	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	Yellow	1015	7	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	Yellow	1015	7	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
4	Yellow	1010	8	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
5	Yellow	1005	9	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
d- The 4th day:										
N	Color	SP. GR.	pH	Sugar	Acetone	Albumin	Bile Pig.	Blood	Pus	Crystals
1	Yellow	1015	7	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	Yellow	1015	7	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	Yellow	1025	7	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
4	Yellow	1005	9	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
5	Yellow	1005	9	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil

Table 12. Kidney functions analyses after 4 days (1, 2, 3 = 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants mixture, respectively, 4= Control and 5 = Positive control (Lafurex: Furosemide Ampules, 40 mg/kg/day), n= 6 rats.

Test	1	2	3	4	5
Urea	37.50±3.30	43.00±2.00	44.20±2.15	44.20±2.50	59.00±4.10
Creatinene	0.96±0.07	1.05±0.10	1.08±0.08	1.22±0.05	1.13±0.09

2.6 Antipyretic effects of QURANI plants' mixture [5]

2.6.1 Antipyretic effects of QURANI plants' mixture

Results in Table 13 showed that, the maximum antipyretic effect was obtained by feeding rats with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture (Average temperature =37.012±0.010).

Table13. The antipyretic effect (measured in °C) of QURANI plants' mixture after 0, 1, 2, 3 and 24 hours of induction of fever by yeast extract {1= Control (Non-treated group of rats), 2= Injected group of rats with yeast extract, 3, 4, 5 = Groups of rats those feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture, respectively, and 6 = Positive control group of (Rats those administered paracetamol, 20 mg/kg/day)}, (n= 6 rats).

Time	Groups					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
0 hour	37.280 ±0.040	38.050 ±0.060	37.080 ±0.020	37.200 ±0.020	37.060 ±0.020	37.300 ±0.080
1 hour	37.040 ±0.010	37.700 ±0.050	37.020 ±0.010	37.000 ±0.000	37.00 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000
2 hours	37.140 ±0.030	37.780 ±0.060	37.020 ±0.010	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000	37.020 ±0.020
3 hours	37.220 ±0.080	38.240 ±0.070	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000
24 hours	37.220 ±0.040	38.240 ±0.060	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000	37.000 ±0.000
Average temperature	37.1800 ±0.050	38.002 ±0.060	37.024 ±0.020	37.040 ±0.010	37.012 ±0.010	37.064 ±0.060

2.6.2 Studies of side effects of feeding rats with QURANI plants' mixture on some important organs

2.6.2.1 Weights (in grams) of some important organs

Based on results presented in Table.14, it is clear that, feeding rats with 2, 4 or 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture have not any bad side effect on weights of many important organs under investigation (Heart, Brain, Kidney, Liver, Lung, Spleen, Stomach and Colon).

Table14. Weights (in grams) of some important organs (Brain, Heart and Lung, Liver, Kidney, Spleen and Stomach) of investigated rats {1= Control (Non-treated group of rats), 2= Injected group of rats with yeast extract, 3, 4, 5 = Groups of rats those feeding with 2, 4 and 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture, respectively, and 6 = Positive control group of (Rats those administered paracetamol, 20 mg/kg/day)}, (n= 6 rats).

Organs	Groups					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Brain	0.910 ±0.120	1.050 ±0.100	1.304 ±0.110	1.286 ±0.100	1.223 ±0.100	1.274 ±0.100
Heart+ Lung	1.198 ±0.100	1.668 ±0.130	1.775 ±0.140	1.394 ±0.120	1.736 ±0.130	1.534 ±0.125
Liver	5.494 ±0.210	6.438 ±0.250	5.890 ±0.220	6.344 ±0.240	5.612 ±0.215	5.738 ±0.235
Kidney	0.409 ±0.070	0.656 ±0.060	0.518 ±0.060	0.494 ±0.060	0.519 ±0.060	0.495 ±0.055
Spleen	0.412 ±0.060	0.413 ±0.050	0.778 ±0.100	0.708 ±0.100	0.520 ±0.060	0.738 ±0.050
Stomach	1.145 ±0.120	1.278 ±0.100	1.554 ±0.130	1.376 ±0.110	1.617 ±0.120	1.367 ±0.150

2.6.2.2 Histopathological studies on some important organs of investigated rats

Results of histopathological studies on important organs of investigated rats revealed that, inducing fever by injecting rats with yeast extract, followed by feeding these rats with 2, 4 or 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture have not any bad side effect on these organs (Heart,

Brain, Kidney, Liver, Lung, Spleen, Stomach and Colon).

Figures 43-50 show the normal histopathological structures of heart, brain, kidney, liver, lung, spleen, stomach and colon of fever induced rats (by injecting these rats with yeast extract) those feeding with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture as a good antipyretic agent.

Figure 43. A photomicrograph of a section in heart of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 100).

Figure 44. A photomicrograph of a section in brain of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 200).

Figure 45. A photomicrograph of a section in kidney of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 400).

Figure 46. A photomicrograph of a section in liver of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' Mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 200).

Figure 47. A photomicrograph of a section in lung of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 100).

Figure 48. A photomicrograph of a section in spleen of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 100).

Figure 49. A photomicrograph of a section in stomach of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 200).

Figure 50. A photomicrograph of a section in colon of rat fed with 8 g/kg of QURANI plants' mixture showing their normal histopathological structures (Hx \$ E x 100).

2.7 Preliminary phytochemical screening of the crude extract of the new pharmaceutical product

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the crude extract of this pharmaceutical product revealed its richness of many valuable secondary metabolites such as: flavonoids, alkaloids, anthraquinones, saponins, tannins, cardiac glycosides, iridoids, carbohydrates and/or glycosides, cyanogenic glycosides, sterols and/or triterpenoids, sublimable substances and chlorides and sulphates [8].

3. CONCLUSION

Results of both *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies showed that, all investigated doses have anticancer, antiinflammatory, antipyretic, diuretic, hepatoprotective and hepatocurative effects, these effects have dose dependent manner. Toxicological studies and examination of all important organs of all investigated rats revealed that, this product is too safe at all the studied doses. Preliminary phytochemical screening of the crude extract of this pharmaceutical product revealed its richness of

many valuable secondary metabolites. These Results will lead us to more biological and chemical investigations of this new, cheap and safe pharmaceutical natural product.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Great thanks to all staff members of the Pharmacology Unit, Cancer Biology Department, Egyptian National Cancer Institute, Cairo, Egypt, for their efforts in the *in vitro* evaluation of cytotoxic effects of this extract under investigation against both human colon and prostate cancer cell lines. Also great thanks to all my colleagues in the Animal House Unit, National Research Centre, Dokki, Giza, Egypt, for hosting experimental animals during this experiment. Also great thanks to Prof. Dr. Tarek Abou Shousha, Head of the Pathology Department, Theodor Bilharz Research Institute for his kind support in photographing and examining all histological slides of this study.

REFERENCES

1. The Holy QURAN. The Noble QURAN in the English Language. King Fahd Complex

- for the Printing of the Holy QURAN, Madinah, K.S.A. Translated by Dr. Muhammad Taqi-Ud-Din Al-Hilali and Dr. Muhammad Muslhin Khan. ISSN 9960-770-15-X. 1419 AH.
2. Alam, A. Eman. Patent no. : 1429/2013 (A new Pharmaceutical Product from Plants Mentioned in the Holy QURAN), presented to the Academy of Scientific Research and Technology, Egypt, 11/9/2013.
 3. Alam, A. Eman. Anti- prostate and colon cancer and diuretic effects of QURANI plants' mixture (a new pharmaceutical product). *IJPPS*, 2014, 6 (Supplement .3, Special Issue), 20-24.
 4. Alam, A. Eman. Antiinflammatory Effects of QURANI Plants' Mixture (A New Pharmaceutical Product). *BJPR*, 2015, 6 (4), 269-277.
 5. Alam, A. Eman. Antipyretic Effects of QURANI Plants' Mixture (A New Pharmaceutical Product). *IJPPS*, 2014, 6 (Supplement .3, Special Issue), 25-29.
 6. Alam, A. Eman. Hepatoprotective and hepatocurative effects of the QURANI Plants' mixture (A new pharmaceutical product). *JCPR*, 2015, 7 (3), 1850-1866.
 7. Alam, A. Eman. Toxicological Studies on the QURANI plants' mixture (A new pharmaceutical product). *JCPR*, 2015, 7 (3), 1883-1892.
 8. Alam, A. Eman. Phytochemical Studies on the QURANI Plants' mixture (A new pharmaceutical product). 2017. In Press.